

Preconcentration Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Cadmium with High Molecular Weight Hydroxamic Acids

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A spectrophotometric method for the determination of cadmium in trace quantities with high molecular weight *N-m*-Cl-phenylpalmitohydroxamic acid is described. Cadmium forms a colorless complex with *N-m*-Cl-phenylpalmitohydroxamic acid which is extracted by chloroform at pH 9.0. Cadmium is, therefore, preconcentrated with the hydroxamic acid and determined spectrophotometrically by adding dithizone. The spectral measurements are made at 510 nm and the molar absorption coefficient is calculated to be $3.2 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Effect of pH, reagent concentration, shaking time and diverse ions on the extraction of cadmium is discussed.

CADMIUM occurs naturally in all food stuffs and its concentration therein is increased by pollution of soil and water. Cadmium accumulates in body tissues and has toxic effect in many organs, like kidney, liver, testis, nervous system *etc.*¹⁻³. Hence, it becomes essential to have a suitable analytical method for the determination of cadmium in ppm levels.

For the spectrophotometric determination of cadmium several reagents are utilised⁴⁻¹⁴ but most of them suffer from the interference of common ions, *viz.* Fe^{III}, Ca^{III}, Hg^{II}, Pb^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cu^{II}, Ce^{II}, Ni^{II}, Ag^I, Mn^{II}, *etc.*⁶⁻¹⁴. Hydroxamic acids are potential analytical reagents and have been used for the determination of many metal ions¹⁵⁻²⁸. So far, no data are available for the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of cadmium with hydroxamic acids.

In the present investigation, a sensitive and selective spectrophotometric method is described for the determination of cadmium using dithizone as a colouring reagent.

Experimental

The spectral measurements were made on a VSU 2-P spectrophotometer (C. Z. Jena) using 1 cm matched cells. pH adjustments were made with a Systronics 335 digital pH meter equipped with glass and calomel electrodes. A measurement was made on a GBC 901 spectrometer.

All the chemicals used were of G.R. grade (E. Merck) unless otherwise stated. *N-m*-Cl-phenylpalmitohydroxamic acid (*N-m*-Cl-PPHA) was synthesised as described elsewhere²⁴. A 0.1% solution was prepared in chloroform. A 0.1% dithizone solution was prepared in chloroform. The cadmium solution of $4.95 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ was prepared by dissolving

the state amount of $3\text{CdSO}_4 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in double-distilled water. The cadmium content was determined volumetrically²⁵.

Extraction procedure: Stock cadmium solution (2 ml) was taken in a 100 ml dry separatory funnel and the pH adjusted to 9.0 with 0.05 mol dm^{-3} borax buffer. Then 0.1% reagent (*N-m*-Cl-PPHA) solution (10 ml) was added and the contents were shaken vigorously for 20 min. The phases were allowed to separate and the colourless organic layer was transferred into a 25 ml volumetric flask. The extraction was repeated with 5 ml of the reagent solution to ensure the complete recovery of cadmium. The 0.01% dithizone solution (3 ml) was added to the volumetric flask and finally the extract was diluted to 25 ml with chloroform. The absorbance of the reddish pink coloured Cd-*N-m*-Cl-PPHA-dithizone complex was measured at 510 nm against a reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

The reddish pink Cd-*N-m*-Cl-PPHA-dithizone complex shows a maximum absorption at 510 nm and the molar absorptivity to be $3.2 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Effect of reagent concentration: A 10 ml of 0.1% solution of *N-m*-Cl-PPHA is sufficient for complete extraction of cadmium.

Effect of dithizone concentration: Various amounts of dithizone solution in chloroform were added to the colourless Cd-*N-m*-Cl-PPHA complex and it was observed that 3 ml of 0.01% solution was sufficient for the complete adduct formation.

Absorption spectra: The Cd-*N-m*-Cl-PPHA-dithizone complex shows a broad absorption peak and has a maximum absorption at 510 nm.

Effect of pH: It was observed that the 100 percent extraction *N-m*-Cl-PPHA was obtained at pH 9.0. After the extraction, cadmium was determined in aqueous layer by aas and found complete absence of cadmium.

Effect of shaking time, stability and recovery: A shaking time of 15-20 min was sufficient for the complete extraction of cadmium. The complex remains stable for 5-6 h and the extraction is quantitative.

Beer's law: The calibration curve for cadmium was obtained under the optimum conditions. Beer's law is obeyed within the range 0.15 to 5.0 ppm of cadmium and the molar absorptivity is $3.2 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Effect of diverse ions: In order to judge the sensitivity and utility of the present method the cadmium (0.44 ppm) was determined in presence of (40 mg each) Be^{II} , Mg^{II} , Ca^{II} , Sr^{II} , Ba^{II} , La^{III} , Ti^{IV} , Zr^{IV} , V^{V} , Nb^{V} , Ta^{V} , Mo^{VI} , W^{VI} , Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Sn^{II} , Al^{III} , As^{III} , Bi^{III} , Sb^{III} and Ce^{III} precisely. However, Hg^{II} , Mn^{II} and Pb^{II} interfere in the determination of cadmium. The interference of Hg^{II} is removed by adding ascorbic acid, while Pb^{II} and Mn^{II} were masked with NaF.

Determination of cadmium in environment: The present method has been extended for the cadmium determination in the soil, plant, water and industrial effluents of Nandeshari area of Baroda. These data were compared that obtained with atomic absorption spectrophotometer (aas) (Table 1). For preconcentration of cadmium from industrial waste, a 3 dm³ of the industrial effluent was taken in separatory funnel and cadmium was extracted with 50 ml of the reagent solution as per procedure.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF CADMIUM IN THE ENVIRONMENT

Sample	Cadmium found*, ppm		
	Present method	Standard deviation	Aas method
Standard cadmium	4.50	± 0.05	4.50
Soil	5.00	± 0.08	5.01
Plant	1.00	± 0.05	1.00
Food	0.29	± 0.04	0.28
Industrial effluents	10.35	± 0.09	10.33
Tobacco	1.80	± 0.06	1.78
Metallurgical units	10.60	± 0.04	10.62

* Average of the 10 determinations.

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